

DEVELOPMENT OF A CFRTP TRANSMISSION HOUSING

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ABSTRACT

To optimize the range of electric vehicles the reduction of vehicle mass is an important possibility. Therefore the components of an electrical powertrain, like a typical two stage transmission, have to be optimized regarding their weight but still fulfilling all requirements. A possible way is the substitution of the aluminum housing with materials of lower density.

Carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP) represent an interesting approach due to a good combination of mechanical properties and proven manufacturing processes. The most challenging requirement to a composite gearbox is the fulfillment of the necessary stiffness, especially at temperatures of more than 100°C. This resistance has a significant impact on durability and acoustics of the gearbox and determines its geometrical shape.

In the following project the housing material (aluminum) of a conventional electric transmission is substituted by a fibre reinforced thermoplastic (FRTP). The general approach to reach all requirements of the gearbox consists of an organo sheet (thermoplast) which is overmoulded by a short fiber reinforced thermoplastic material. The use of aluminum inserts as bearing seats allows to transmit the bearing loads into the organo sheet and reduces the deviation of the gear mesh. With additional injection moulding ribs and UD-tapes the stiffness requirements are achieved.

In the morphological analysis of the concept phase several approaches were investigated by using FE analyses and evaluated regarding their feasibility. Stamping and injection moulding simulation was used to assess and optimize the manufacturability. Topology optimizations lead to load path optimized shape considering tension and pressure areas. The derived draft design represented the geometrical basis for the organo sheet layer optimizations, UD-Tape and injection moulding rib placement.

A close cooperation with the tool designers ensured the manufacturability and the first part of the housing could be produced. This takes place in a three-phase process. First the organo sheet and reinforcing UD-tapes are heated up using an IR heating device and afterwards they were pressed in a stamping tool. Waterjet cutting produces the outline of the preform. During the final step the organo sheet is heated again and overmoulded with the optimized rib geometry to finalize the part.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the most important measures to increase the range of electric vehicles is the reduction of overall vehicle weight. The intention of this project was to reduce the weight of a gearbox significantly by replacing the aluminium of the gearbox housing by a lighter material. As stiffness is one of the most important requirements for a gearbox housing, it seems to be obvious to use carbon fibre reinforced plastics with thermoset plastic matrices.

Unfortunately, carbon fibre reinforced plastics with thermoset plastic matrices have some important disadvantages. The cost for this material is very high. Compared to an aluminium cast part the price for a fibre reinforced part is factors higher. Second, the production time, e.g. in RTM technology, is very long, times 10-20 longer than the production of an aluminium casting part. Especially in mass production with high volume, this is a severe reason not to use thermoset technology.

A production process that is very cost effective for high volume production and can be implemented into the cycle time of a mass production plant is injection moulding. The process time is close to the process time in casting. A second process with the same advantages is hot pressing of organo sheets.

Using organo sheets, it is possible to implement carbon or glass fibres in an orientated way into a plastic part. This provides additional stiffness to the part. In combination with thermoplastic overmoulding, nearly every geometry or functional detail can be added to the hot pressed organo sheet. So, the combination of both processes should derive a part that has high stiffness and all necessary functional details needed.

Concerning stiffness, there is one disadvantage of the upper processes. Both work with thermoplastic matrices. The main target of the project was therefore to examine the possibility to show the feasibility of function and production in a process that can be industrialised.

As a demonstrator we chose a gearbox housing used in an electric vehicle, which means not only high loads, but also high temperatures, of more than 100°C, for the housing material. The aim was to replace only the housing, all interior parts have been reused and work as proper as in the aluminium gearbox housing (see figure 1).

In this project the companies ARRK P+Z, ARRK Shapers, ARRK SPG and ARRK UK worked together to also show the ability of the ARRK product development group to develop the parts, to build the tools, to set up the production process and to produce in a small series production size. ARRK P+Z was responsible for the engineering, ARRK Shapers set up the production process, build the tools and the prototype.

The engineering approach used in this development process was, to use simulations to push decisions forward. To do this we used different types of simulations like finite element method, moulding simulation, stamping simulation and optimization. The development engineer, who was a CAE engineer, had to be able to do or at least to steer these kind of simulation. The interpretation of the results and the decision for the next steps had to be taken by this CAE engineer in discussion with a team of composite experts of different disciplines (e.g. Design, Testing, Simulation, Composite, Manufacturing)

Overall the approach of a CAE driven development worked out very well. With a minimum of design work, it ended up with a prototype of the cover that is fulfilling all requirements.

Figure 1: Aluminum gearbox and CFRP cover prototype

2 DEFINITION OF RELEVANT LOADCASES

To start it was necessary to set up the most important load cases of the gearbox that have the biggest influence on the housing geometry. These are, in this case, the maximum torque load cases in drive and coast situation.

The maximum torque is 130Nm at the input side for drive load case. With the given gear ratio, we derived an output torque of 1300Nm.

For coast, we estimated a torque of 50Nm at the input shaft, which gives us a torque of 500Nm on the output shaft. This is a reasonable value for light cars with a short wheel base.

For the calculation of the torque load cases we applied the loads on the input shaft and fixed the rotation of the output shafts. As we considered a simplified gear contact, drive and coast did not impose symmetrical forces into the gearbox housing (see figure 2). Therefore it was necessary to check both load scenarios in every step of the project.

Nevertheless, as we can see from the pure values of the torque, it is clear that the drive load case is more important for the optimization of the gearbox housing than the coast load case. In the topology optimization for example, drive and coast loadcase have been taken into account but the influence of the coast load case was not significant.

Additionally we examined gravity load cases with 30g in z direction and 10g in x direction to simulate a crash situation and to examine the stability of the fixation of the gearbox to the car body.

To examine the impact of the torque load cases on the housing a model of the original gearbox with all the internal parts was build. This included shafts, bearings, gears, housing parts and the fixation at the car body. The geometry of the original gearbox was derived by disassembling the real part and scanning the housing geometry in a reverse engineering procedure.

Figure 2: Qualitative radial and axial loads in the gearbox housing (blue drive, red/white coast).
Additionally a result of the topology optimization can be seen left hand.

3 SIMULATION MODEL

In all simulations in every phase of the project, we simulated the whole gearbox model. This includes all housing components (e.g. shafts, gears, bearings, screws, see figure 3). As it is important for the distribution of the forces in the gearbox housing, contacts were defined nonlinear. The coupling of the gears was simplified by connection elements which contained the gear mesh stiffness. In this way we avoided the usage of cutting forces not considering the load change due to local stiffness

changes. All simulations have been done in ABAQUS, except optimizations which were performed with OPTISTRUCT.

Figure 3: Shell model of the gearbox in concept phase with electric engine housing and body mounting including interior parts

4 TARGET VALUES

There are three important performance targets for a gearbox: Efficiency, durability and acoustics. For all these three disciplines the quality of the gear mesh has a very significant impact. In an ideal gearbox there would be no deformation of the housing by the transmitted loads and no manufacturing tolerances. In such a gearbox, the tooth geometry could be designed for an optimal efficiency. In a real gearbox the transmitted loads cause deformations of the gearbox housing and also position tolerances lead to a deviation of the bearing positions. Any displacement of those bearings of the shafts leads to a change in position of the gears running on that shaft.

Figure 4: Model of shafts and bearings. The main declination errors occur between the intermediate and the output shaft of the gearbox.

Depending on the direction of the displacements, this leads to a misalignment of the gear mesh. To have a proper gear mesh in a deformable gearbox the teeth of the gears compensate the deformation of the gearbox using e.g. crowning. The changes of the gears should be as small as possible to keep the

efficiency of the gearbox as high as possible. Therefore the design of the teeth and the gearbox stiffness are always adjusted to each other.

In our project, this means that we have to reach the same stiffness values with the new housing material as in the original aluminum gearbox. In terms of gear mesh, this means that the relative displacement between two shaft bearings have to be lower than in the aluminum gearbox. Axis deviation and axis inclination errors (see figure 5) of the intermediate and output shafts (figure 4) have to be on the same level or below the values in the aluminium housing.

Figure 5: Definition of axis inclination error as used in the project [KISSsoft].

5 MATERIAL SELECTION

The material for the housing has to fulfil several requirements. First of all the stiffness has to be high, not only at room temperature, but also at about 100°C. Also cost is an important criterion for the selection of the material. As we were planning to use organo sheet and an overmoulding process, we had to select the organo sheet material and the thermoplastic moulding material.

The stiffness of the material depends on the kind of fibres and the matrix used. We expected glass not as a suitable fibre, which was also a result of the simulations in the concept phase. The glass fibre reinforced material showed about 50% of the stiffness of the carbon fibre reinforced material. Reaching the required stiffness seemed to be only possible by increasing the thickness of the Organo sheet over 5mm, which was not possible due to the hot stamping process in production. Due to these findings, we concentrated on carbon fibre reinforced material.

Our first plan was to use material with fibre orientation 80% in tensile direction to be able to put the fibres into the load direction. As this was not available on the market, we used equilibrated fabrics with 0°/90°/45°/-45°/-45°/45°/90°/0° stack and optimized the thickness of the layers. The organo sheet was available in thickness up to 5mm. As thermoplastic moulding material, we chose Grivory with 40% fibre volume that shows good performance at the required temperature.

The material parameters for the simulation were taken from the information provided by the material suppliers. At high temperatures material data was available for Grivory but not for the organo sheet material. That has been estimated in the first place using a linear laminate calculation tool.

6 PROJECT PHASES

The project was divided into four phases. The first phase was the concept phase. In this phase the basic simulations and a morphological box (Figure 6) to set up the concepts that followed in the next phase has taken place. At the end of this phase the concept decision considering the results of the morphological analysis was made. The second phase was the design phase. In this phase we followed

the concepts from the concept phase in parallel. The original housing design was changed completely according to findings from optimization and simulation or engineering decisions. In the end of this phase there was the final design decision. The third phase was the detail design, putting all details into the final part design. In the fourth phase, the production of the prototype, we build the tools and set up a production process showing first ideas how to industrialize the manufacturing of the gearbox.

In the beginning of the first phase we checked the general feasibility of our plans. We scanned the original gearbox housing and build up a FEA model in ABAQUS. In this model we replaced aluminium by the organo sheet material. We were mainly looking at the inclination and deviation error on the intermediate and output shafts. Using this model we retrieved the following important results: Glass fibre showed a very low performance concerning stiffness, so we decided to concentrate on carbon fibre reinforcement. Knowing that we did not optimize the housing yet, we decided to give glass fibre a second chance with an optimized housing shape. Also with an optimized housing the stiffness was not satisfying.

Looking at our target values the housing part on the engine side was quite stiff. Most of the problems occurred from the cover of the gearbox. Here, the most critical load case was the drive loadcase resulting in a torsion of the gearbox that the cover could not prevent efficiently. The target value with the biggest impact on all decisions was the axis inclination between the intermediate and the output shaft.

Figure 6: Analysis of different solutions in the morphological box.

Morphological box (Figure 6): The first simulation results were put in a morphological box. There we set up the main functions we have to check for a feasible concept. For each of these parameters there are several solutions, fulfilling the function using different approaches. After having found the feasible sub-solutions, they were combined to an overall concept. Then, these concepts were evaluated, using a ranking and a weighting matrix.

The main parameters in the morphological box for the gearbox were the following: Design space, loads (mechanical, thermal), functional design, environmental topics, costs, maintenance. The three main concepts (we investigated over all five concepts) that were investigated had the characteristics as can be seen in the figure below.

From the morphological analysis we decided to go on with concept 1 and 3 (Figure 7). The main reasons for this decision were:

Concept 1 offers the highest potential for weight saving and cost saving and surely the lowest production time.

Concept 2.1 and 2.2 didn't show the full potential of the thermoplastic fibre reinforced matrix material in combination with the carbon fibres. The direct metal link between the bearing seats puts all stiffness requirements into the metal part. This would surely work, but is not the aim of the project.

Concept 3 is a good compromise between a solution for the "weak point" bearing and the stiffness potential of our housing material. Both, cost and weight would be on a good level, nevertheless, feasibility has to be proven.

Concept	1	2.1	2.2	3
Description	Low cost concept	Cage insert concept - GFR	Cage insert concept - CFR	Separate bearing insert concept
Details	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -current gears, bearings, sealing -metal insert for bearing seat -glass fiber organosheet -screwed flanges (housing/cover) -2 inserts for each screw -dowel pin for housing/cover centering -engine served to housing, containing by surface -simple air drain potbook with tube to avoid oil loss -air drain potbook also used for oil (no fill) -defined oil volume -smart lubrication concept -measuring oil temperature at oil drain plug -measuring bearing temperature at drilled holes -direct surface temperature measuring 			
Ranking				
Issue	Scaling [1-5]	Single Rating [1-5]		
Material costs	4	2	3	4
Manufacturing costs	4	2	3	4
Mass	4	2	3	4
Precision	3	2	3	4
Stiffness	3	2	3	4
Inspection/	3	2	3	4
Maintenace	3	2	3	4
Sum	71	79	75	80
Ranking	4	2	3	1
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -low cost -low mass -no milling of flanges necessary (compensation w/ glue) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high stiffness and strength at bearing seats -high precision and centering precision due to canneted bearing seats -insertion of gear mesh possible -further cost reduction for screws possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high stiffness and strength at bearing seats -high precision and centering precision due to canneted bearing seats -glass fiber/carbon fiber organosheet possible -insertion of gear mesh possible -further cost reduction for screws possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -adequate stiffness -adequate precision -insertion of gear mesh possible
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -low stiffness and strength at bearing seats -only glass fiber organo sheet possible (thermal expansion) -no inspection possible due to glued flanges -no direct oil level measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high costs -high mass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high costs -high mass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -high costs -high mass

Figure 7: Final rating of the main three concepts investigated.

Going on with phase 2, the design phase, we checked the feasibility of concept 1. Unfortunately, the results showed, that it is not possible to reach the necessary stiffness between intermediate and output shaft without using metal bearing seats. That was the main reason for not going on with concept 1 in the design phase and concentrated on concept 3 using metal inserts at the bearing positions.

To derive a new housing geometry and a suitable fibre layout, we set up an optimization simulation. In the topology optimization (Figure 8) we also used load cases drive and coast.

We minimized strain energy and set the weight as a constraint. Additionally we set the axis deviation and the axial inclination error as a constraint for the optimization. This way, we derived the main load paths that are responsible for the stiffness performance of the gearbox housing.

As we wanted to optimize a fibre reinforced part, we would like to have only tensile stresses in our housing and no compressive stresses. Therefore we used the possibility to use higher constraints for compressive stresses than for tension stresses.

In a separate investigation, we tried to see the influence of this procedure. Overall the effect was not too big and did not show load paths that were very different to the ones we got from using an equivalent stress value. The inclination is mostly dominated by the torsion of the gearbox housing. So tensional stresses are dominant for this constraint.

Figure 8: Results of topology optimization and derived geometry.

From the optimization, we derived the geometry for both parts of the gearbox. This geometry was used to build up a simulation model for the detailed design. For all following simulations and optimization we concentrated on the cover. We also investigated measures on the second part of the housing, but these measures did not show a significant improvement. The cover is the critical part in the stiffness chain.

The constraints coming from production were already implemented in this design. These were mainly maximum degree of deformation in the cover, minimum radii and a maximum wall thickness of the organo sheet. The constraints are defined through the stamping step in the production process.

After setting up this geometry, we optimized layer thickness in the organo sheet. The optimization showed, that $\pm 45^\circ$ layers should be the thickest ones (Figure 9). This is in good correlation with the fact, that the torsion in the housing is the main deformation causing the axis inclination error.

Figure 9: Results of the layer thickness optimization showing the importance of the +45° layers to prevent torsional deformation (red colour shows highest thickness areas).

As the stiffness derived from the optimization of the organo sheet was not satisfying, we decided to implement UD tapes and additional ribs into the geometry (Figure 10). The idea was to lower the torsional deformation with these two measures. The ribs were placed into the part in the overmoulding process step. The UD tapes must have a good connection to the organo sheet. This is possible if they are part of the hot stamping process.

Figure 10: Different models for investigating the use of UD tapes and ribs (left). On the right hand side the derived final part.

For an optimal torsional stiffness with minimum additional UD tapes we investigated several variations. Taking costs into account we ended up with two UD tapes crossing between the two critical shafts. After implementing the crossing UD tapes, the desired stiffness values could be reached. Also a

further reduction of the organo sheet thickness was possible by using these local reinforcement measures.

Afterwards the detailing phase started with the following design: Bearing seats with aluminium, separation of aluminium seats from the carbon fibre organo sheet in the overmoulding process with the glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic matrix and thermoplastic ribs on the cover from the overmoulding process. Crossed UD tapes were also introduced in the hot stamping process.

In the detailing phase all missing details of functional fixing points and connections were made. For the connection of the two housing parts we introduce inserts that have been placed after the overmoulding process. The flange, the dowel pins and the functional faces have been detailed.

To optimize the production process and to check the manufacturability, a stamping simulation was performed (Figure 11). Here we made sure that we would have no significant issues concerning the stamping process and we could derive a starting cut for the raw organo sheet before stamping. The idea is, to have minimum waste of organo sheet material in a series production process. The results from the stamping simulation were promising. Also the injection moulding process has been checked in several Moldflow simulation cycles (Figure 11). Based on this the shape of the TP matrix parts has been optimized to guarantee a good filling with the TP matrix material in all regions.

At the end of the detailing phase all relevant load cases including operating and overload cases (e.g. gravity loads) have been checked and all requirements were fulfilled.

Figure 11: Results of the injection and the stamping analysis

The production of the preform of the cover was done in three steps (Figure 12): Heating of the organo sheet and UD-tapes up to 240°C. This was done by an IR heating device. Both components, organo sheet and UD-tapes, are fixed in a frame with guiding slots for the tapes to keep them in the correct position. The stamping was done in a preheated stamping tool with an operating temperature of about 100°C. After the stamping the part is post-processed with waterjet cutting to its final shape.

Figure 12: Heating and stamping of the organo sheet. After stamping the water cutting finishes the preform for overmoulding.

Before overmoulding the pressed organo sheet is heated up again. Heating up the pressed organo sheet ensures a good connection between the thermoplastic matrices of the injection moulding material and the organo sheet matrix. In the overmoulding step the inserts for the bearing seats are inserted into the tool and fixed by the overmoulding (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Heating of preform with stamping tool and overmoulding of organo sheet including aluminium inserts.

To reach the required tolerances flanges, bearing seats and centering sleeves had to be post-processed in a milling step. To be able to assemble the prototype for illustration purposes the second half of the gearbox housing was produced out of PMMA for the first prototypes (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Rear side of the gearbox assembly showing the housing part made from PMMA

7 CURRENT/NEXT STEPS

Although the development took place for the full gearbox only the cover has been manufactured due to the challenging time schedule. To complete the assembly also the second part will be produced to test the complete assembly and maybe bring it into the car to do full vehicle testing. Currently the

investigation of thermal heating, energy loss and acoustics is not representative because of the differing housing stiffness made from PMMA for the moment.

To show the capability of the first part testing has started. In a first step the material data of the undeformed organo sheet is tested followed by preformed specimen tests. In a final step the first part will be tested with an equivalent static load representing the operating loads (Figure 15). In parallel the CAE approach will be validated to the real component behaviour.

Figure 15: Design of component test rig for validation of manufactured part to CAE model

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